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of North East India Studies

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GAUHATI UNIVERSITY INSTITUTE OF
NORTH EAST INDIA STUDIES

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CONTENTS

1. Azan Fakir, Sufi Literature and Assam: A Historical Discourse
Syeda Mehnaz Jahan & Susmita Hazarika 1-16
2. Ethnic Tensions and Political Turmoil: Analyzing Violence in Manipur
Priyanka Singh 17-36
3. Reshaping Educational Horizons: A Post-Reform Study of
Public Funding Trajectories in Assam's Higher Education
Prapti Borthakur, Sagartirtha Chakraborty & Suresh Kumar Nath 37-55
4. Food Heritage of the Tai-Khamti of Arunachal Pradesh: A Study on the
Traditional Food Preservation Methods
Nada Aka 56-69
5. Changing Pattern of Games and Amusement: A Comparative
Study between Pre-Colonial and Colonial Assam
Trikha Rani Das, Pulen Das, Epabi Baruah & Amrita Bora 70-86
6. The Exotic North East, Their Women, and Capitalist Racism in India
Ratna Huiem & Kathiresan Loganathan 87-102
7. Conceptual Metaphors of Menstruation in Assamese, Mising
And Bodo:A Cognitive Perspective
Bisalakshi Sawarni 103-117
8. The Aiding Touch: Study of a Promotional Organisation's Role in
the Creation of Tea Producer Companies (TPCs) in the Udalguri
District of Assam (India)
Bidyut Bikash Kataki 118-136
9. The Chothe of Manipur: History, Myth and Memory
Mareem Thoril Chothe & Nilakant Singh 137 -148

The Exotic North East, Their Women, and Capitalist Racism in India

Ratna Huiem*
Kathiresan Loganathan**

Abstract: The northeastern region of India is often showcased as a land of pristine beauty, and exotic landscape; inhabited by tribes in multi-coloured garments, displaying their rich and unique culture. However, underdevelopment underlines the region, frustrating the typical northeast youth in a rapidly globalising world and creating despair, and a sense of hopelessness. Undoubtedly the region has grown. Yet, it remains a laggard in terms of economic opportunities for today's youth, who prefer employment in a classic workplace. Thus, capitalism entices these young people and they set out for the mainland for lucrative education and employment. The difference in language, culture, and above all, the racial phenotype of the northeastern people stands out. These bio-physical and cultural markers intersect with various other sociological variables. It is in this background that the race debate is presented, arguing that it is indeed real and could get worse as consumerism and capitalism thrive. The women of the region must not end up as exotic oriental showpieces in the vast urban mainland of India. The much prized 'cosmopolitan self-presentation' of the people of the North East is a coveted asset for the rising personal care and hospitality industries. Their cosmopolitanism is sought after by these capitalistic establishments as they can easily gel with capitalistic consumerism. What merits attention is that this should not be the harbinger of corporatised and racialized slaves.

Keywords: Cosmopolitanism, Globalisation, Intersectionality, Migration, Racial formation

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Nestled in the northeastern frontiers of India, eight states comprise the North East region. These are Arunachal Pradesh, Assam, Manipur, Meghalaya, Mizoram, Nagaland, Tripura, and Sikkim. They are distanced by geography, the racial phenotype, and hence from the popular imagination of what constitutes the idea of India. There is now a wilful avoidance of the word Mongoloid; but that is the race that typifies much of the people of the North East (NE). ‘Slit’ eyes, ‘flat’ nose, and small build, are the physical characteristics that are conjured up in the mind about the NE people. Violence-torn, anti-assimilationist, underdeveloped, and alienated are what characterizes the imagination about the NE region by those from the mainland.

‘Chinky’, a racial slur, and several other lewd and offensive remarks have often been a part of abuses directed at northeasterners, and especially at women. The Government of India declared ‘chinky’ as racist in 2011. They also declared that those using it are chargeable under the Scheduled Castes and Tribes (Prevention of Atrocities) Act, 1989, and could face five years imprisonment (Kikon, 2021). Calling a NE person ‘chinky’ upfront, may have therefore declined, but perceptions cannot be changed overnight. Nonetheless, open name-calling and shaming have declined largely as more NE people intermingle with the rest of India. Participation in both national and international events, media coverage, and a hyperactive social media have prompted the creation of greater awareness about the people from this region. However, racial profiling during COVID-19, and targeted attacks on people from the NER, especially on women, was rampant (Haokip 2020; Lalrinawmi & Shuchi, 2022; Niumai, 2023). Embedded deep within society, racism can thus repeatedly rear its ugly head.

Footnote Racism and Headline Racism

There is the concept of “footnote racism” (Ngaihte, 2015, p.15), where racially charged prejudices are often presented in covert ways. These often miss attention, especially of the non-northeasterner. Day to day interactions are often peppered with jibes, layered taunts, gawking, staring, comments about appearances, and food habits etc. These constitute footnote racism. The other concept is “headline racism” (Ngaihte, 2015, p.15), where there is an unleashing of violence and frontal attacks, often by mischievous and unruly individuals. As per media reports, such violent engagements have been common amongst the young student community in institutional premises or hostels, which presumably are relatively safe spaces. There had been a violent attack on a young male first year Architecture student from Manipur in a Bangalore hostel in 2012, over a trivial argument about viewing an IPL match. Dana Sangma

from Meghalaya who was studying at Amity University, New Delhi, committed suicide due to racial targeting after allegedly having been caught cheating in the exam in 2012. Then there was the killing of 20-year-old Nido Tania from Arunachal in 2014, at the Lajpat Nagar market in Delhi, for reacting to mocking comments about his appearance. These are just a few instances of racist attacks in India by Indians on another ‘category’ of Indians. Although these are now in the past, what is important is that the existence of footnote racism acts as a precursor to headline racism. Thus, both footnote and headline racism can be latent and manifest in different temporal and spatial contexts. However, footnote racism is embedded in the mindset while headline racism lurks dangerously and can emerge anytime.

Owning Mary Kom to Quell Racist Ideas

The NER represents a diversity of people who have long been outside the Indian imagination. The natives also identify themselves thus. It is indeed ironic that 2012 was the year that Mary Kom, the internationally feted boxing champion from the NE brought laurels to India by winning the 2012 Olympics boxing bronze medal. In the same week, when Mary Kom was feted, thirty thousand NE people who were working in various Indian cities had to flee home fearing racist attacks. However, this did not stir the Indian imagination as such an exodus pertained to the ‘other’ which lay outside their imagination. The ‘exodus’ did not provoke much discourse on racism within India. Paradoxically, the success of Mary Kom as an Indian citizen who represented the nation on the world’s stage was invoked to defend any dissent on racism against the NER and its people (McDuie-Ra, 2015b).

In 2012, the then Prime Minister, Manmohan Singh even hosted a delegation of NE migrants in the backdrop of the attacks on them. He, however, did not acknowledge racism as a motive for the attacks. Furthermore, the Home Ministry declared that things have been taken care of under the provisions of the SC/ST Act. But, not everyone from the NER is covered by this provision. Racist orientations have a different genesis and must not be confused or clubbed with one’s caste or tribe. Nonetheless, terms such as ‘racial profiling’, and ‘targeted attacks’ against the NE people started gaining prominence. The media started noting it and the sheer coincidence of Mary Kom’s glory on a stage as dynamic as the Olympics, juxtaposed with the racial exodus, created a furore.

Racializing and Disowning Mary Kom

Mainland India was waking up gradually to this otherised sub-culture of people who hardly looked Indian or did Indian ‘stuff’. Increased mobility,

particularly of people from the NER into various other states in the mainland, especially for education and lucrative employments have increased the exposure to the NE. However, when Omung Kumar directed a documentary on Mary Kom in 2014, Priyanka Chopra, a Bollywood actor was cast in the role, rather than someone from a similar ethnicity. This too had racist hues. It was perceived that the movie will not be a box-office hit if a well-known 'mainstream Indian' face was not cast as Mary Kom. This shows the failure to embrace Mary Kom wholeheartedly, in the attempt to erase her basic identity and ethnicity, while focussing on saleability.

McDuie-Ra (2015b) lucidly captures Mary's travails with fame, femininity, and her overpowering performance in the masculine sport of boxing. She was projected at that time as the typical strong NE woman that can represent India not only in the sports arena, but also as an ambassador for peace and unity within India, when the racial exodus occurred. Yet, she was only half-owned.

An Emergent Racism Syndrome

The racism problem has deepened in contemporary times. Increased flow of NE out-migrants into various Indian cities for education and employment, increased interactions, exposure and understanding, has resulted in a decline and near-absence of the earlier name-calling, shaming, questioning of nationality etc. However, what is equally noticeable and alarming is the way the Indian mainland is increasingly viewing the people from the NER, especially the women, in highly sexualised roles. NE women are also perceived as promiscuous, vying for male attention, given their unchaperoned mobility in the metropolises, and their sense of fashion and style.

Ngaihte (2015) elucidates how business process outsourcing (BPO) and other private sector businesses, which prioritise proficiency of the English language, seem tailored for the NE people, as majority of them have the requisite skill sets. McDuie-Ra (2012b) adds that during 2005 to 2011, a twelve-fold increase in out-migration from the NE to Indian cities was recorded. Around half a million NE people reside outside the region. Migrants from the region are highly visible in the retail, hospitality, airline, and call centre industries. Violence in the northeastern region, easier availability of work in the big cities, and the possibility of pursuing higher education have been luring the people of the NE from the relatively lower economic class to migrate. Such movement of the NE people into the mainland has exposed them to a world quite different from those in the hills of the NE.

Furthermore, the young NE woman is now increasingly being tapped as full of potential, especially in the hospitality industry. She is projected as the 'exotic' oriental service-provider; sometimes donning the Chinese *Cheongsam*, or the Japanese *Kimono*, the Sikkimese/ Tibetan *Bakkehu* etc. However, it has never been the homegrown Assamese *Mekhla-chadar*, the Manipuri *Phanek*, the Khasi *Jainsem*, or the Naga *Aꯁꯪ Jangup Su*. Likewise, stylishly turned-out NE women attend to customers at international fashion boutiques, wait on the rich and affluent at equally exotic locales and spas. A misty air of the Orient is created in India to enhance sales. Marchang (2011) notes that 62% of the workforce in the national capital is comprised of female migrant workers from the NER who are engaged in a variety of services in the hospitality sector. Dolly Kikon (2018) too mentions how study participants highlighted that cultivating an image and appearance that synchronised with what is associated with fine dining experience is an important part of their identity. Working in an upscale Japanese restaurant, it was reiterated that body language, turnout, confidence, and displaying a sense of authenticity was essential to wait at a table where only the very well-travelled and highly affluent converge. Additionally, she remarks how indigenous immigrants from the NER, despite the social and political hierarchies, were readily absorbed in the world of fine-dining in a globalised India. Restaurants that served Asian food specifically looked out to employ these migrants from the North East.

The NE woman due to her relatively fairer skin tone, is perceived as more desirable. It follows the patriarchal patterns of desire where lighter skin is privileged (hooks, 2003). Deori and Rajagopalan (2016) note how even in the UK labour market, recruitment is based upon ethnicity and skin tone. Stereotyping and historical perceptions about gender, race, and class also determine the categorisation of the service provider. They further add that female NE migrants were confident of a more lucrative employment as compared to their male counterparts, owing to the sexualised roles expected of them in the beauty-care industry. Additionally, emotional attributes like patience and gentleness are considered a bonus in working in the beauty industry. Thus, both the physical and emotional attributes create a socio-cultural profile in job-seeking. The fairer skin tone and the distinct appearance serves to give them an edge. The authors also mention that during their field work, customers explicitly stated their preferences for staff from the NER. Furthermore, McDuire-Ra (2012b) observes that in India, sectors such as hospitality, beauty, and personal care, employ huge numbers of NE migrants, consequent upon their Asiatic appeal.

Deconstructing the Racial Formation in India

Racism is generally perceived as static and often assumed to be on the wane across societies. What is disturbing are the emergent paradigms of racism. Instances of increased assimilation, and lack of structured racism are cited. The original configuration of racism is deflected by contemporary society. However, debates and discourses abound about the inter-relationship between racism and slavery.

In the entire racial formation, there are short-term advantages that racialized workers can gain. However, the long-term implications are different (Bonilla-Silva, 1997). In the context of the NE, the relatively advantaged position they appear to be getting owing to their lighter skin tone, familiarity with the English language, sense of style and fashion, and their 'un-Indian' looks, are mere short-term gains. Entrenched within this preferential treatment for stereotyped jobs in the hospitality and personal care sector, is a racist attitude. The long-term implications look rather ominous. As several thousands of youths begin to migrate out to the mainland and very few return, there is an increasing fear amongst the older generation that the land and its people stand at risk of losing indigeneity and ethnicity which are threatened by the possible absorption into mainstream India.

An alternative framework for understanding racial phenomena is evident where economic, political, social, and ideological levels are impressed upon by the placing of a group of individuals in certain racial categories. Races typically are identified by their phenotype, but what qualities are attributed and what position is accorded in society to a specific racial group is sociological, rather than biological. Racialization is woven into various structures and these have significant repercussions. Racism, which is often treated as merely a flawed ideological concept, has strong hierarchical foundations. The race that is accorded superiority tends to receive greater economic remuneration and access to better occupations and/or prospects in the labour market, enjoys better leverage in the political system, is usually perceived as better and smarter. Thus, such ingrained perceptions and practices acquired and learnt through socialisation and culture make up the racialised structure of a society (Bonilla-Silva, 1997).

It may appear on the surface that racist practices have ceased since overt practices such as name calling and shaming have come down. However, what is more dangerous is the covert racism that cannot be easily understood, identified, or apprehended, as these practices are shrouded by benign exteriors. Presenting the NE youth as the most affable, adaptable, and suitable for the hospitality and personal care industry is just another face of racism. An easily procurable

human labour that suits the service requirements, couched in a discourse of the mystic and exotic orient, often bordering on erotica, is clearly racism in another guise and has potential for serious repercussions.

Racist practices are manifestations of collective racist perspectives and thoughts. Many studies on racism ignore or overlook the internal divisions that permeate through different races and gender as well. Thus, there are divisions and hierarchies that create a super-ordinate race and a sub-ordinate race within various social groups. History is replete with racialisation within social systems where class and gender have played significant roles. Whether racial factors override class and gender, or vice versa, depends upon several other economic, political, social, and ideological factors. The general character of participation and the proportion of participation in all domains of social life of different racial groups must be evaluated to arrive at a true understanding of a racialized social structure and system.

Neo-Racism and Intersectionality

Racialisation has been a historical and political process involving colonization, slavery, bonded servitude, and labour immigration in more contemporary times. Hence, racial practices are no more determined by biological markers, but more specifically by societal markers associated with one's identity. New forms and modes of racialisation are emerging as social and political formations evolve and intersect. These in turn intersect with class and gender stratifications and further complicate societal transactions and relations in a racialized society.

The youth migrants from the NER absorbed in the hospitality and personal care sectors are racialized to make them believe that they are superior to the other working class from the rest of India who do not possess lighter skin, fashion sense, and English language abilities. The fact that the young NE woman is induced to don the exotic looking attires of the other East-Asian countries to wait on the elite of the mainland, is nothing but racialized servitude. If the 'different-looking' appearance of the people from the NER is what boosts sales and returns, then she should be donning her ethnic tribal outfits. If traditionality and cultural representation is to be invoked, her own homegrown rich traditions must be preferred over those of other nations. Thus, class and gender too get racialized. The other lurking danger is that of the perception that may soon come to bear upon those from the mainland; the fear that the people from the NE are taking away their jobs. This has ominous portents.

The character of the racialized social system and the counter struggles of the oppressed or subordinate race will determine what course racism takes. The

struggles maybe social, political, economic and/ or ideological. It may be a combination of all. The individual or collective experiences of racism generally results in various struggles at the societal level, which garners political mileage. This is achieved only when individual and collective struggles manifest as overt protests. Racism meanwhile continues to imbue life into rigid dogmas, which operationalise themselves to become common sense (Omi and Winant, 1994). These continue to set the rules of interaction with the subordinate race in a racialized society, inhering a set of social relations and practices at all levels. This becomes ideology, which is then manifested as racism.

Marking Out the North East

Owing to the vast differences in culture and geography between the NE and the mainland, and the distinct 'bio-physical markers', the NE people prefer to reside amidst their own ethnic groups. There is ease of access in terms of jobs, accommodation, and such other initial 'settling down' issues. It can be friends from back home, relatives, work colleagues, or colleagues from the Church. They maintain these relations as a part of survival strategies and socialisation. Such an inclination to 'keep within their own groups' is interpreted by the mainlanders as anti-assimilative (McDuie-Ra, 2012a, 2012b). But it is to be noted that such practices of ethnic preferences abound across all cultures.

Another pertinent thing that irks the NE people, especially the girls, is the perception that NE girls are of loose moral character. Since the NE women work in environments that accentuate their sexualities, mingle freely with members of the opposite sex, and are mostly on their own, being far away from home, they are perceived as immoral. McDuie-Ra (2012b) highlights how the NE women work in settings where they are almost on display to titillate the male gaze and citing Pavero refers to these as 'places of voyeurism' (2005, p. 167). The NE women typically work in restaurants and malls. Men who would ideally not have access to these women, often come to feast their eyes on their highly sexualised presentations. The NE men, contrastingly, are often viewed as violent and impulsive.

Potential violence in the form of verbal, physical, and sexual assaults haunted them until the early 2000s. Awareness brought in by media discussions and government sponsored goodwill building, owing to the backlash from continuous spates of violence and retaliation by the NE student community, supported by the NE migrants across India have somewhat altered the current scenario. Another major concern is that violence against NE people are mostly underreported, misreported, or never reported. Often they are held responsible

for the violence in terms of either provocative dressing or conduct. Retaliating to oral taunts, groping, molestation, or any kind of assault, shifts the blame to the victim.

Handling Alienation Through Racial Bonding

An important aspect of northeastern migration are the troubled frontiers from where they come. Having lived in heavily militarised zones back home, they feel they can handle the sporadic violence against them in the mainland. But they feel terribly let down as racism against them is lost in the din of racism against Indians who go abroad; either Non-Resident Indians, or Persons of Indian Origin. They thus end up reconciling to the despair that they face racism in their own country. Tolerance, avoidance, and endurance, or at worst retaliation seem to be the only way out.

However, unwilling to be passive victims, the NE people actively network amongst themselves to tap the increasingly expanding retail, hospitality, and grooming industry. They are closely knit through shared food habits, places of worship, culture, and preferred dwellings. Additionally, they are employed in common sectors. They have also managed to create a kind of image about their existence unlike the regular migrant from other places such as Bihar or Uttar Pradesh, who would be willing to engage in very menial work and often reside in slums. The NE migrant aims for much more.

Out-Migration from the NER and Employment

Scholars have been focussing largely upon in-migration into the NER through its porous borders. Out-migration to highly urbanised cities in the mainland have been less endorsed, and not as well analysed. It is a cause for concern as it can have multiple effects upon the indigeneity of the NER. NE migrants had mostly been from among the well-to-do in the initial years of migration owing to aspirations for better education and better employment opportunities through competitive exams. However, the increasing spate of young migrants seeking employment in the retail, personal grooming, and hospitality industries are major causes of concern.

Lusome and Bhagat (2020) note that as per the 2011 Census, 28% of out-migrants from Assam, and 25% from Manipur, moved out for work. They also add that 52% of the migrants are from urban areas. This perhaps accounts for the fact that most of the NE out-migrants are English-speaking, and hence are preferred by the service industry, besides their ethnic appeal. Furthermore, they add that 526 thousand migrants have moved out of the region.

Approximately 47% migrants from Tripura and Manipur moved to the six urban centres of Delhi, Kolkata, Greater Mumbai, Hyderabad, Bangalore, and Chennai.

Mistri (2022) also highlights that the 2011 Census shows significant labour force supply, out-migrating from the NER. They reiterate the unique case of North East out-migration when it comes to inter-state migration. Almost 0.54 million people from the region migrated to the mainland in 2011. A substantial 30 per cent of such migration was for livelihood, besides another huge volume of student migration. Those who migrated to avoid ‘conflict, political unrest, and natural calamities’ comprised of 13 per cent. He further computes that as per migration by place of last residence, there were a total of 1.03 million out-migrants from the NER, who were inter-state migrants.

Several studies have noted that most of the north-east migrants come to Delhi prior to college education, on their own; and at times with siblings (Marchang, 2011; Usha and Shimray, 2010; Remesh 2012). They also note that migration rates of both men and women are of similar proportions. The reasons for migration despite the felt alienation in the mainland are of deep concern. Ongoing ethnic strife and violence, lack of better education and employment opportunities, corruption, the thriving of legal and semi-legal economies, overall low levels of development have been the push factors (Loganathan and Huiem, 2022). According to Census 1991, the percentage of migrants to Delhi from the region was 0.05, which rose by 0.17 during the 2001 Census. The 2011 Census also reflected a constant outflow of NE migrants. It was reported that the total out migration to Delhi specifically from the region within 2005-2011 had increased twelve fold within these five years. Unfortunately, there are no recent figures available.

The NE people are good at “locational masking”, as call centre staff are expected to neutralise their accents. Therefore, BPOs are another common sector of employment for them. The NE accent mostly differs from the mainstream Indian accent. Moreover, being on their own, without family and being young also help them to be mobile and accede to the odd work hours (McDuié-Ra, 2012a). However, increasing out-migration and urbanisation, to settle for years, or maybe for generations in another land which they perhaps can never call their own homeland, owing to racial alienation, is another point of concern.

Exoticizing the NE Women

The representation of the various tribes in different advertisements or depictions in museums always portray a similar pattern: backward and exotic. Their colourful and unique attire with the natural and pristine beauty of the NER is emphasized but their history is obliterated. It is also noteworthy that during the 2010 Commonwealth Games held in Delhi, the placard holder donned

the traditional Mizo dress, the *Puanchei*, as it was assumed it will give a unique look. However, the person wearing it was someone who did not represent the racial group. Such selective appropriation and disowning of the marginalised NE people can be perceived as footnote racism. McDuie-Ra (2012a) additionally documents how NE people, especially, women, are gaped at, making them feel like some exotic species. He reports them as stating how extremely unnerving it is; but over time, have forced themselves to get accustomed to it.

Furthermore, there are observations about the many myths surrounding women from the NER. The demands of the sexualised roles of the hospitality and retail sector converge very well upon the ‘exotic-looking’ NE women. Fashion conscious and smartly turned out, the women get easily absorbed into these industries. However, their enhanced visibility in these sectors are attributed to their distinct physical and racial characteristics (Mcduie-Ra, 2015a). Hence, there is no denying that such ‘ethnic economies’ have been created.

The women of the North East are cast in the same stereotyped mould as other East Asian women, especially by the West. They are perceived as most suitable for patriarchal male libidinal gratifications, where the Asian woman is portrayed in a hypersexualised image. Such images of these women have assumed global connotations through various media formats in an increasingly globalised and interconnected world. This is yet another instance of footnote racism. The deeply sexualised imaginations about the NE women further add to such positive discrimination in labour markets ranging from the hospitality and beauty industries, personalised elite care such as spas, who also seek to employ the urbane, light skinned, English speaking NE woman, as discussed earlier. Meanwhile, negative discrimination exists in terms of housing, police involvement, or any form of violence. Their vulnerabilities as a migrant, lack of political capital, majority of them being non-propertied with a marginalised presence in the Indian city setting, increase their chances of negative discrimination. Safety and security of the NE women in the residences they hire and live in, are also of great concern (McDuie-Ra, 2015a).

Unwanted and lewd comments about their appearances, especially of NE women, being ridiculed to often depict them as ‘stupid’, projecting the NE men as hostile and violent, were the predominant stereotypes of racist conduct. Tourism departments and museums exoticize the NE, especially the tribes. The media accords attention to the NER only when it deals with terror issues. It is otherwise considered politically and culturally insignificant (McDuie-Ra, 2012b).

Food Racism

Another major issue faced by NE people is food. Fermented and ‘smelly’ food like bamboo shoots, fermented fish, and soyabeans are staple in their daily diets and hence are often subject to ridicule. Abuse and taunts are common. Dolly Kikon and Karlsson (2019) and Debbarma (2016) talk about food racism and how NE food needed to be mostly cooked and consumed in a concealed manner. Their food is often looked at with abhorrence and disdain as most of it is fermented, has a distinct odour and is labelled as dirty food (Kikon, 2021). A mismatch with the archetype of the Indian face further alienated them, which also acted as distinct markers of pinpointed targeting for consuming smelly food. Noticeably different cultures added to the sense of alienation. Transforming the food culture of a meat loving NE people, and trying to undermine their fermented cuisine by labelling it as unclean or foul in appearance and taste is indeed racialisation of a society. Teltumbde (2009) writes about how cooking and eating that are so basic to any individual and community life, when frowned upon, marks discrimination and inequalities. Housing societies and institutional canteens refrain from plating up this food as it is equated with contamination, filth, and being unclean. Such practices place the community who consume this food at a lower level of the social hierarchy.

Capitalist Racism and Colonisation of Ethnic Labour

Systemic racism is instrumental in structuring society (Saldanha, 2011). Denial, deflection, or avoidance, worsens the problem further. Racial phenotypes are absolute markers in the global wealth distribution scenario. These amplify repercussions on social and economic capital formation. Denial by policy makers and scholars alike worsen the racial formations. Increased globalisation and migration have brought in cosmopolitanism and the hybridisation of cultures within and across nations. However, the race hierarchy continues to work to determine income and education levels, as well as political participation. Saldanha (2011) further argues that it is foolhardiness to assume that racism is mere prejudice. It thrives all around us in many ways. Environmental and housing racism, propelled by patriarchy and capitalism, prevail in the new geo-political landscape. Thus, he reiterates that race is determined by much more than just genotype, phenotype, perceptions, or socio-economic characteristics.

Migrants from the NER are rather unique. They do not join the ranks of slum dwellers or squatters despite the enormity of the urban megapolis. With not much to call their own, the city they live in remains an alien land, where they continue to battle for survival, retaliating when required, and endorsing the adoption of safety measures and practices as survival strategies. They present

themselves with a highly cosmopolitanised demeanour which also works well to challenge the 'backward' stereotypes that form the Indian imagination of the NE dweller. Stylishly turned out with impeccable fashion sense, and a passion for western music, they are envied by many outside their racial formations. However, as Karl Marx and Friedrich Engels noted the dangers of cosmopolitanism lie in its destructive powers to ravage traditional culture, literature, and civilizations. The neoliberal representations of urban cities and townships are examples of cosmopolitanism, where it seeks to erase the old, traditional, and historical character of geographies. Caught in this milieu of the march towards capitalistic societies, the NE job seeker, invariably falls prey to the designs of capitalist racism and colonisation of their labour.

Cosmopolitanism and the NE Cultural Landscape

McDuie-Ra (2012b) also talks about an emergent pan-northeastern identity, that assumes subaltern proportions. He discusses the complexity of the experiences faced by these migrants in the socio political and economic spaces that they inhabit, where discrimination often stems from capitalism. He also reiterates the disjoint between the lived experiences and the cosmopolitanism of the NE migrants, who continue to be racialized. Globalisation, consumerism, and a booming media seem to be working at erasing cultural differences, the creation of a common global culture, and increased cosmopolitanism. However, what is worrisome is that the race hierarchy cannot be easily written off; nor will it dissipate easily.

Anasma Gayari (2022) talks about the hybridisation of cultures as a product of neo-liberalism, capitalism, and cosmopolitanism. She also discusses the unshakeable racialized identities that the NE migrant carries, and how they are unknowingly lured into labour which manifests racial colonisation and racial capitalism. Globalised cities enchant these migrant workers as they navigate their ways out of their troubled or underdeveloped homelands. They fall prey to the needs of the expanding global and cosmopolitanised capitalistic ventures, which seek to create a mystic orient in a range of contemporary global labour markets. As historicizing of the NE has been rather poor, it is indeed a frightening thought that cosmopolitanism may usurp their indigeneity.

Racism can assume myriad manifestations. Owning and yet disowning Mary Kom; pushing patriarchal patterns of desirability and sexuality; casting ideal beauty frames; and creating hierarchies of super-ordinate and sub-ordinate race are some of them. The youth of the NE are often portrayed as indulging in self-isolation, mixing only amongst themselves, not mingling enough etc. Yet they are much preferred for employment in specific sectors, where they are

more 'on show'. The sexualities of the NE women are hyper-represented, donning skin-tight attires meant to appease the male gaze. Attempts are made to represent different locales of the various Asian nations through them and representing the exotic orient within India itself. Thus, labour is racialized under the overarching dominance of capitalism and cosmopolitanism. They are typecast in certain ethnic economies or sectors, which especially require women to work during odd hours and serve the clientele in close proximity. The outcome is that they are often blamed provocative conduct. Racial formations are systemic and a racialized society can serve to create a capitalistic colony out of the NER. Racialization is a historical and political process. Colonization of a labour force will serve to create bonded servitude. Further studies will serve as drivers for reforms in undoing racial formations and prevent the deepening of ruptures in society. The misrepresentation of the NER as totally inhabited by tribes that alienate themselves from India must stop. The ethnic troubles in the NER must be sought to be understood rather than be written off as mere aberrations.

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